

Some Methods for Yager Preference Involved Aggregations in Multi-Criteria and Multi-Sources Evaluation

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Abstract

OWA operators and related aggregation techniques generally focus on input vector with a linear ordering. However, in commonly faced multi-criteria and multi-sources evaluation and decision making, the inputs involved form an evaluation matrix.

Considering the fact that the data under evaluation are all with two dimensional meanings, this study explores and proposes four novel preference involved aggregation techniques by using RIM quantifiers and OWA operators. The first two models are both with two steps to carry out the aggregation processes, with one using two times of OWA operators and another considering evaluation matrix as a vector lattice. The last two models come from a whole perspective to direct the aggregation processes, with one arising from a global magnitude view and another based on staggered ordering using two specially defined collections of permutations. Illustrative examples and remarks are also spotted immediately following the proposed models or at suitable positions.

Keywords: Aggregation function; decision making; evaluation method; multi-criteria and multi-sources evaluation; Ordered Weighted Averaging operator.

1. Introduction

As commonly known, evaluation techniques and methods are cornerstones of decision making and management. Reasonable, effective and acceptable comprehensive evaluation results for certain objects under evaluations will provide efficiencies, supports and even directives to decision makers and managements, helping them to do more convincible and discretionary decisions. Hence, the evaluation functions and methods based computational intelligence [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8] can offer considerably many decision aids in numerous management areas such as project management and personnel management.

1.1. *Aggregation functions as one major tool in evaluation problems*

Aggregation functions (also known as aggregation operators) [1], as a hot area of research, play underpinning roles in performing numerical and comprehensive evaluation. Roughly speaking, when decision makers evaluate an object and obtain a related evaluation result for that object, often they need to consider or juggle through several values coming from different sources, with all seemingly possible or reasonable. They sometimes hesitate and wonder what value will be the most representative based on those values from different sources. In another decision scenario where multiple criteria are considered when making an evaluation for some certain object, the multiple criteria may hinder decision maker from developing or gaining a holistic and comprehensive view or assessment to that object under evaluation. As an important decision aid and evaluation tool, aggregation function serves as an ideal mechanism to comprehensively merge through several independent values and returns a single one, which may be helpful and instructive to decision makers.

Aggregation functions with related researches and numerous applications have been burgeoning in recent decades [1, 8, 18, 12, 13, 14]. In their typology, aggregation functions

can be chiefly divided into four main classes: disjunctive functions, averaging functions, conjunctive functions and mixed functions. For example, the well-known t-conorm and t-norm [1] are representatives of disjunctive and conjunctive functions, respectively. A disjunctive function will always return a value that is not less than any of the inputs; while a conjunctive function will definitely yield a result that is not larger than any of the inputs. It is noteworthy that disjunctive functions and conjunctive functions are dual of each other, and thus the studies for each type will be dually applied to one another. Apart from some other uses, disjunctive and conjunctive functions are more used in logic reasoning based techniques such as fuzzy logic and approximate reasoning [1, 16]. Mixed functions also have some characteristics and different behaviors such as uninorms. In this work, we will only focus on averaging functions which, from their several inputs, always return a value that is between the largest input and the smallest input of theirs.

1.2. Yager preference aggregation and OWA operators

The subjective preferences very often are consciously or unconsciously involved in the processes of evaluating and decision making, because the long time experiences of decision makers may be embodied in their preferences. Actually, preferences involved decision making and their effects on aggregation techniques have been analyzed by Yager in part via the proposal of Ordered Weighted Averaging (OWA) operator [17]. Formally, OWA operators do not only belong to the class of averaging functions, but they are also special cases of the Choquet integral [9] with respect to symmetrical fuzzy measures [1]. Some further theoretical extensions or studies of OWA operators can be found in a large number of literatures, e.g., in Jin et al. [18], Lizasoain and Moreno [19], and Mesiar et al. [20].

Given a weight function representing the relative importance between concerned criteria or sources, the commonly known Weighted Averaging (WA) operator (also known as Weighted Mean) assigns each single weight to each input, not according to some inherent feature of input such as its value or magnitude, but from some general match-up such as the input index variable. For example, assume w is a weight function and x is an input function, then the WA operator with respect to w will be given by the expression $WA_w(x) = w(1)x(1) + \dots + w(n)x(n)$, as we are quite familiar with. With the same weight function, OWA operator, different from WA operator, will associate each input a weight according to the inherent magnitude of it; put simply, the OWA operator with respect to w is defined by the expression $OWA_w(x) = w(1)x(\sigma(1)) + \dots + w(n)x(\sigma(n))$ where σ , as a special function conducting the positioning and weights associating, is an appropriate permutation of the indices $\{1, \dots, n\}$.

In the past three decades, due to their flexibility and feasibility in preference involved decision making, OWA operators have been widely carried out in astonishing variety of applications such as decision making and evaluations [21, 5, 16, 17] and image processing [10, 14], among others [8, 22, 23, 24].

The fast acceptance of OWA operators by practitioners may partly thank to the proposal of a very convenient and effective measure called orness [17] together with some other measures such as dispersion [17], all introduced by Yager. It is noticeable that recently Jin et al. proposed some other important measure called Scatter [3] which highlights on its fuzzy affinity and some other advantages. Returning to orness measure, this measure can very well and suitably indicate the optimism extent to which any OWA operator or OWA weight function embodies. Although this experience is not absolutely accurate unless with some additional conditions, we generally can observe the desired fact that the OWA operator with larger orness will result in larger aggregation result.

Nearly most of the methods to generate OWA weight functions are related to orness measure, including Ouyang [25], to name a few. Those functions can very well embody a type of bi-polar preference, e.g., optimism/pessimism preference [17] and certainty/uncertainty preference [6, 11]. Conversely, the diverse weight function generation methods also provide a wide range of choices and suggestions to decision makers. It is interesting that such preferences were ingeniously and effectively modeled with another method proposed by Yager, merely using some monotonic functions on unit interval called Regular Increasing Monotone (RIM) quantifiers [26], which, with their application and theoretical extensions, also have been further fathomed and developed [5, 27]. In addition, the Induced Ordered Weighted Averaging (IOWA) operator is another generic concept which has some further ramifications such as distance induced and norm induced OWA [8, 21, 28].

1.3. OWA aggregations in multi-criteria and multi-sources evaluation

This article focuses on a classical type of multi-criteria and multi-sources evaluation problem, the Multi-Criteria and Multi-Sources Evaluation (MCMSE) problem. Note that it is often mentioned in Multi-Criteria Group Decision Making (MCGDM) problem, but in this study we still make some differences between these two related concepts; that is, the differences are made in two aspects: (1) MCMSE is only an evaluation problem which is the major part of decision making practice, and (2) MCMSE is a more general concept which may be specified into some detailed evaluation models such as Multi-Criteria Group Evaluation (MCGE) problem.

In MCMSE problem, commonly we need the following prerequisites (i.e., the conditions that must be known in advance):

- (i) a criterion set C , containing n criteria C_i ($i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$) on which our evaluation problem is restricted;
- (ii) a source set S , including m sources S_j ($j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$) from which each single evaluation emerges or is obtained; and

(iii) some values (i.e., opinions, judgments or single evaluations, etc) provided from each source for each criteria, which can form a matrix E called *Evaluation Matrix* throughout this study.

Apart from the information given above, we also need to determine the following information about relative importance, which can be expressed by weight functions or fuzzy measures [1, 2]:

- (i) a relative importance between those n criteria in C ; and
- (ii) a relative importance between those m sources in S .

Very often the relative importance can not be obtained or there are subjective preferences of decision makers involved, thus OWA aggregations can be well suited in such situations. For example, we may have two bipolar preferences, one for criteria C_i , the other for sources S_j ; those two preferences can be different and can also be in a parallel or an ordered way as later we will analyze. This study will in detail discuss some different methods using OWA aggregations in MCMSE problem, suggesting different choices of preference aggregations for decision makers and practitioners to use.

The remainder of this study is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses preferences in aggregation functions and OWA aggregation, with some interlaced reviews and remarks for necessary definitions. In Section 3, we introduce two two-step models for preference involved aggregation in MCMSE problem, with one having some similarity to general processes of MCDM problem while the other is involved with vector lattice information. Section 4 draws the attention to some whole-consideration perspectives to viewing MCDM problem wherein only one RIM quantifier embodying decision maker's preference will be applied. Section 5 concludes and remarks this study.

2. Preferences in Aggregation Functions and OWA Aggregation

Without loss of generality, the aggregation functions discussed in this study are defined to be multi-variable functions that always revolve around unit interval and its power extensions. We firstly fix some terminologies about input functions which in evaluations are often the inputs to be aggregated from multi-sources or multi-criteria.

Definition 2.1. In this work, an n -dimensional input vector is also regarded as a function $x : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$, called *Input Function* (of dimension n); for possible convenience, the vector form and the function form of an input may be used interchangeably as in convention. In addition, the space of all input functions (of dimension n) is conventionally denoted by $[0, 1]^n$.

Definition 2.2 ([1]). (Aggregation function) An n -ary aggregation function A is a mapping $A : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that satisfies the following two conditions:

(i) (Boundness) $A(0, \dots, 0) = 0$, $A(1, \dots, 1) = 1$;

(ii) (Monotonicity) For any $x, y \in [0, 1]^n$ with $x < y$, we have $A(x) \leq A(y)$.

The space of all n -ary aggregation functions is denoted by $\mathbf{A}^{\langle n \rangle}$.

Definition 2.3. (Averaging function) An n -ary averaging function F (also known as averaging operator) is a function $F : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that for any $x \in [0, 1]^n$,

$$\min(x) \leq F(x) \leq \max(x).$$

It is implied that any averaging function F is idempotent, i.e., $F(a, a, \dots, a) = a$; conversely, a monotone idempotent function F is always averaging. These properties well conform to the common intuition of many decision makers when carrying out evaluations.

In numerous evaluations, preferences are frequently involved since they are very embodiments of the experiences, subjectivities or emotional biases of decision makers which can be changeable or contingent according to decisional situations.

Definition 2.4. A *weight function* w (of dimension n) is a mapping $w : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^n w(i) = 1$.

Associating each with a given weight function, two special averaging functions, Weighted Averaging (WA) operator and Ordered Weighted Averaging (OWA) operator, are reviewed in the following, respectively.

Definition 2.5. (Weighted Averaging operator) An n -ary Weighted Averaging operator associated with weight function w (of dimension n) is a function $\text{WA}_w : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\text{WA}_w(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n w(i) x(i). \quad (1)$$

Definition 2.6 ([17]). (Ordered Weighted Averaging operator) An n -ary Ordered Weighted Averaging operator associated with weight function w (of dimension n) is a function $\text{OWA}_w : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\text{OWA}_w(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n w(i) x(\sigma(i)), \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\}$ can be any suitable permutation that satisfies for any $1 \leq i < j \leq n$, $x(\sigma(i)) \geq x(\sigma(j))$.

The weight functions w in both WA and OWA operators embody some types of preferences of decision makers, and the preference for OWA operators is bipolar since we actually regard $\{1, \dots, n\}$ as a linearly ordered set $\{1, \dots, n\}$, while generally it is not the case for WA operators.

As an important measure for OWA operator, the orness/andness effectively and efficiently embodies the extent to which decision makers have the strengths of their bipolar preferences, i.e., the extent of their optimism/pessimism attitudes. Furthermore, in general the larger orness, the larger result the OWA operator will return.

Definition 2.7 ([17]). (Orness/andness of OWA operator) The *orness* of the n -ary OWA operator with weight function w is defined as

$$\text{orness}(\text{OWA}_w) = \sum_{i=1}^n w(i) \frac{n-i}{n-1}. \quad (3)$$

The *andness* of the n -ary OWA operator with weight function w is defined as the duality of its orness

$$\text{andness}(\text{OWA}_w) = \sum_{i=1}^n w(i) \frac{i-1}{n-1} = 1 - \text{orness}(\text{OWA}_w). \quad (4)$$

Yager [26] introduced a useful and flexible method to generate weight functions for OWA operators to be associated.

Definition 2.8 ([26]). (RIM quantifier) Any Regular Increasing Monotone (RIM) quantifier Q is a monotonic non-decreasing function defined on unit interval $Q : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $Q(0) = 0$ and $Q(1) = 1$.

Definition 2.9 ([26]). (OWA operator with RIM quantifier) An n -ary OWA operator with RIM quantifier Q is a mapping $\text{OWA}_Q : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\text{OWA}_Q = \text{OWA}_{w_Q}$, where OWA_{w_Q} is the n -ary OWA operator with weight function w_Q , called *Q -generated weight function* and satisfying

$$w_Q(i) = Q(i/n) - Q((i-1)/n). \quad (5)$$

The orness and andness of this OWA operator with RIM quantifier Q are defined the same as the orness/andness of OWA_{w_Q} :

$$\text{orness}(\text{OWA}_Q) = \text{orness}(\text{OWA}_{w_Q}), \quad (6)$$

$$\text{andness}(\text{OWA}_Q) = \text{andness}(\text{OWA}_{w_Q}). \quad (7)$$

Definition 2.10 ([27]). (Quasi-orness/andness of OWA operator with RIM quantifier) For any $n \geq 2$, the *quasi-orness* (q -orness) of an n -ary OWA operator with RIM quantifier Q is defined as

$$q\text{-orness}(\text{OWA}_Q) = \int_0^1 Q(t) dt. \quad (8)$$

Correspondingly, the *quasi-andness* (q -andness) of an n -ary OWA operator with RIM

quantifier Q is defined as the duality such that

$$q\text{-andness}(\text{OWA}_Q) = 1 - \int_0^1 Q(t) dt. \quad (9)$$

The orness/andness of the OWA operators with the same RIM quantifier but with different dimensions can be slightly different according to the dimensions of those OWA operators, and the quasi-orness/andness of OWA operator with RIM quantifier is always a constant. In addition, when the dimension n becomes very large, $\text{orness}(\text{OWA}_Q)$ can be very near $q\text{-orness}(\text{OWA}_Q)$ [26]. Recall that a monotonic function defined on compact intervals is surely Riemann Integrable. Moreover, the use of Riemann Integral in (8) and (9) can be more evident when Q is absolutely continuous. Also recall that when Q is absolutely continuous, there necessarily exists an integrable function q on unit interval as a distribution such that $\int_0^t q(y) dy = Q(t)$; and Liu [5] calls it the generating function of RIM quantifier Q .

3. Two-Step Models for Preference Involved Aggregation in Multi-Criteria and Multi-Sources Evaluation

As we briefly stated in the Introduction, a classical comprehensive evaluation problem involves two major dimensions from which every single evaluation arises. The two concerned dimensions involve criterion and source which can often be regarded as having symmetrical roles. That is, since every single piece of evaluation can be obtained under one certain criterion and from one specific source, then an evaluation matrix can be naturally built either by rows presenting criteria and columns indicating sources, or by the reverse order with rows presenting sources and columns indicating criteria. Thus, for a given evaluation matrix, we can choose to firstly aggregate the single evaluations in each row to obtain some intermediately aggregated evaluations, and then aggregate those intermediate evaluations to obtain a final evaluation; or we can also choose to firstly aggregate the single evaluations in each column and so forth. Due to the duality in it as assumed, we may only need to consider one choice, for example, firstly aggregating row evaluations and then going with the column dimension.

In the rest of this section, we discuss two relevant models; one of them uses twice OWA operators, and the other one firstly considers a Vector-valued OWA (V-OWA) operator and secondly an OWA operator.

3.1. Two-step model for preference involved aggregation in MCMSE using two times of OWA operators

In MCMSE problem, let $C = \{C_i\}_{i=1}^n$ be the criteria set, $S = \{S_j\}_{j=1}^m$ be the source set, and $E : \{1, \dots, n\} \times \{1, \dots, m\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be the mapping called *Evaluation Matrix* such that $E(i, j)$ is the single evaluation under criterion i and of source j . Note that each row in evaluation matrix can be also regarded as an input function/vector $E_i : \{1, \dots, m\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ ($i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$) such that $E_i(j) = E(i, j)$. In this problem, there are two optimism/pessimism preferences, one related to sources and the other to criteria. Suppose these two preferences are modeled by using two RIM quantifiers, Q_S for sources and Q_C for criteria, respectively. By the simplicity in its structure, in the following we directly present the procedures to form this model.

Model 3.1. Two-step model applying twice RIM quantifiers.

Step 1: For each $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, use the OWA operator with a RIM quantifier Q_S to aggregate an input vector E_i and obtain $x_i = \text{OWA}_{Q_S}(E_i)$.

Step 2: Apply the OWA operator with a RIM quantifier Q_C with obtained x_i ($i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$) to aggregate (x_1, \dots, x_n) and obtain a result $\text{OWA}_{Q_C}(x_1, \dots, x_n)$.

Example 3.1. Consider a 4×3 evaluation matrix

$$E = [E(i, j)] = \begin{pmatrix} 0.6 & 0.9 & 0.4 \\ 0.8 & 1 & 0.5 \\ 0.7 & 0.4 & 1 \\ 0.3 & 0.2 & 0.5 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Assume the two involved RIM quantifiers Q_S and Q_C are equal and satisfy $Q_S(t) = Q_C(t) = t^2$ (for every $t \in [0, 1]$). Using (5), the Q_S -generated 3-nary weight function w_{Q_S} can be obtained with $w_{Q_S} = (1/9, 1/3, 5/9)$, and the Q_C -generated 4-nary weight function w_{Q_C} can be obtained with $w_{Q_C} = (1/16, 3/16, 5/16, 7/16)$.

Step 1: For each $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, use OWA operator with RIM quantifier Q_S to aggregate input vector E_i and obtain

$$x_1 = \text{OWA}_{Q_S}(E_1) = (1/9)(0.9) + (1/3)(0.6) + (5/9)(0.4) = 0.522,$$

$$x_2 = \text{OWA}_{Q_S}(E_2) = (1/9)(1) + (1/3)(0.8) + (5/9)(0.5) = 0.656,$$

$$x_3 = \text{OWA}_{Q_S}(E_3) = (1/9)(1) + (1/3)(0.7) + (5/9)(0.4) = 0.567,$$

$$x_4 = \text{OWA}_{Q_S}(E_4) = (1/9)(0.5) + (1/3)(0.3) + (5/9)(0.2) = 0.267.$$

Step 2: Apply OWA operator with RIM quantifier Q_C with obtained x_i ($i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$)

to aggregate (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) and have result

$$\begin{aligned} \text{OWA}_{Q_C}(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) &= (1/16)(0.656) + (3/16)(0.567) + (5/16)(0.522) + (7/16)(0.267) \\ &= 0.42725. \end{aligned}$$

3.2. Two-step model for preference involved aggregation in MCMSE with vector lattice

Before introducing the next two-step model, we review some recently developed approaches to perform OWA aggregation on lattice values.

As for lattice values, in this study we only focus on vector lattice which has some simpler structures and properties. Recall in earlier evaluation matrix, $E_i : \{1, \dots, m\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ ($i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$) satisfying $E_i(j) = E(i, j)$ is just a vector value in vector lattice $(\{E_i\}_{i=1}^n, \preceq)$, where \preceq is defined such that $E_k \preceq E_s$ if and only if $E_k(j) \leq E_s(j)$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$. Unlike real values, it is possible that neither $E_k \preceq E_s$ nor $E_s \preceq E_k$ holds, i.e., E_k and E_s are not comparable. Note that $E_k \prec E_s$ means $E_k \preceq E_s$ and $E_k \neq E_s$. On the other hand, once a weight function is obtained and assigned to $\{E_i\}_{i=1}^n$, the convex combination $\sum_{i=1}^n w(i)E_i$ is always meaningful because a vector multiplied by a real value is equal to a new vector, with each of its entries equal to the corresponding original entry multiplied by that value, i.e., $a \cdot (x_1, \dots, x_n) = (a \cdot x_1, \dots, a \cdot x_n)$. Seeing those vectors as the similar objects to real values, OWA aggregation clearly is still suitable and useful.

Hence, the remained problem lies in how to devise effective and reasonable weights generating methods. The following two approaches address this problem from different perspectives.

Approach 1 [15]: Admissible Permutations.

Let $(\{E_i\}_{i=1}^n, \preceq)$ be a vector lattice considered in this study, a permutation $\sigma : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\}$ is called *admissible* (with respect to $(\{E_i\}_{i=1}^n, \preceq)$) if

- (i) for every $E_i \prec E_j$, we have that $\sigma^{-1}(j) < \sigma^{-1}(i)$, and
- (ii) for each E_i , the set $\{\sigma^{-1}(j) \mid j \in \{1, \dots, n\} \text{ with } E_i = E_j\}$ is an interval in \mathbb{N} .

The set of all such admissible permutations is denoted by T_E .

Then, let w be a weight function (of dimension n), a *Vector-valued OWA* (V-OWA) operator with RIM quantifier Q , $V\text{-OWA}_Q : ([0, 1]^m)^n \rightarrow [0, 1]^m$, in our evaluation problem is defined such that

$$V\text{-OWA}_Q(E_1, \dots, E_n) = \frac{1}{|T_E|} \sum_{\sigma \in T_E} \sum_{i=1}^n w_Q(i) \cdot E_{\sigma(i)}, \quad (10)$$

where $|A|$ denotes the cardinality of any finite set A , and w_Q is the Q -generated weight function.

Approach 2 [18]: Set functions L and U .

Let $(\{E_i\}_{i=1}^n, \preceq)$ be a vector lattice relevant to this work. Firstly define two set functions $L : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow 2^{\{1, \dots, n\}}$ and $U : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow 2^{\{1, \dots, n\}}$ such that

$$L(i) = \{r \in \{1, \dots, n\} \mid E_r \prec E_i\}, \quad U(i) = \{r \in \{1, \dots, n\} \mid E_i \prec E_r\}. \quad (11)$$

Secondly, define function (not necessarily normalized) $v : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ satisfying

$$v(i) = \frac{Q((n - |L(i)|)/n) - Q(|U(i)|/n)}{n - |L(i)| - |U(i)|}, \quad (12)$$

where Q is a given RIM quantifier representing optimism/pessimism preference with respect to criteria. Lastly, a V-OWA operator $V\text{-OWA}_Q : ([0, 1]^m)^n \rightarrow [0, 1]^m$ (with Q) in this approach is defined as

$$V\text{-OWA}_Q(E_1, \dots, E_n) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n v(i) E_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n v(i)}. \quad (13)$$

In the following, selecting Approach 2, we present the procedures of using V-OWA in MCMSE problem.

Model 3.2. Two-step models for preference involved aggregation in MCMSE using V-OWA operator and OWA operator.

Step 1: For each $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, use V-OWA operator with Q_C (for criteria) to aggregate (E_1, \dots, E_n) to obtain $x = V\text{-OWA}_{Q_C}(E_1, \dots, E_n)$, a m -nary real valued vector.

Step 2: Employ OWA operator with RIM quantifier Q_S (for sources) to aggregate $x = (x_1, \dots, x_m)$ and have preference involved comprehensive evaluation $\text{OWA}_{Q_S}(x_1, \dots, x_m)$.

Example 3.2. Still with the 4×3 evaluation matrix $E = [E(i, j)]$ and RIM quantifiers Q_S and Q_C as in Example 3.1, we go through the next two steps.

Step 1: Using (11), we have

$$\begin{aligned} L(1) &= \{r \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\} \mid E_r \prec E_1\} = \emptyset, \\ U(1) &= \{r \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\} \mid E_1 \prec E_r\} = \{2\}; \\ L(2) &= \{r \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\} \mid E_r \prec E_2\} = \{1, 4\}, \\ U(2) &= \{r \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\} \mid E_2 \prec E_r\} = \emptyset; \\ L(3) &= \{r \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\} \mid E_r \prec E_3\} = \{4\}, \\ U(3) &= \{r \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\} \mid E_3 \prec E_r\} = \emptyset; \\ L(4) &= \{r \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\} \mid E_r \prec E_4\} = \emptyset, \\ U(4) &= \{r \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\} \mid E_4 \prec E_r\} = \{2, 3\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, using (12), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
v(1) &= \frac{Q_C((4-0)/4) - Q_C(1/4)}{4-0-1} = \frac{Q_C(1) - Q_C(1/4)}{3} = \frac{1 - 1/16}{3} = \frac{5}{16}, \\
v(2) &= \frac{Q_C((4-2)/4) - Q_C(0/4)}{4-2-0} = \frac{Q_C(1/2) - Q_C(0)}{2} = \frac{1/4 - 0}{2} = \frac{1}{8}, \\
v(3) &= \frac{Q_C((4-1)/4) - Q_C(0/4)}{4-1-0} = \frac{Q_C(3/4) - Q_C(0)}{3} = \frac{9/16 - 0}{3} = \frac{3}{16}, \\
v(4) &= \frac{Q_C((4-0)/4) - Q_C(2/4)}{4-0-2} = \frac{Q_C(1) - Q_C(1/2)}{2} = \frac{1 - 1/4}{2} = \frac{3}{8}.
\end{aligned}$$

Subsequently, using (13), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
x &= V\text{-OWA}_{Q_C}(E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^4 v(i)E_i}{\sum_{i=1}^4 v(i)} \\
&= \frac{(5/16)(0.6, 0.9, 0.4) + (1/8)(0.8, 1, 0.5) + (3/16)(0.7, 0.4, 1) + (3/8)(0.3, 0.2, 0.5)}{(5/16) + (1/8) + (3/16) + (3/8)} \\
&= \frac{(5)(0.6, 0.9, 0.4) + (2)(0.8, 1, 0.5) + (3)(0.7, 0.4, 1) + (6)(0.3, 0.2, 0.5)}{5 + 2 + 3 + 6} \\
&= \frac{(8.5, 8.9, 9)}{16} = (0.53125, 0.55625, 0.5625).
\end{aligned}$$

Step 2: Employ OWA operator with RIM quantifier Q_S (for sources) to aggregate $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$ and have preference involved comprehensive evaluation

$$\text{OWA}_{Q_S}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = (1/9)(0.5625) + (1/3)(0.55625) + (5/9)(0.53125) = 0.54306.$$

4. Whole-Consideration Induced Aggregation in Multi-Criteria and Multi-Sources Evaluation

In Section 3, we considered some approaches using two steps of aggregation since the concerned evaluation matrix has two dimensions and the corresponding aggregation requires using two times RIM quantifiers. In this section, we discuss two methods for whole-consideration induced aggregation in MCMSE problem. In general, by whole-consideration we mean only using one RIM quantifier to perform the whole preference involved aggregation, rather than using two RIM quantifiers with two sequential steps.

4.1. Whole-consideration OWA aggregation for evaluation matrix from a global magnitude view

In the following model, we do not distinguish criterion dimension and source dimension; that is, when there are n criteria and m sources, the input function we will consider is nm -nary.

Model 4.1. Whole-consideration OWA aggregation considering nm -nary input function.

Step 1: Given an $n \times m$ evaluation matrix E , select a desired RIM quantifier Q representing the optimism/pessimism attitude of decision maker.

Step 2: Create the nm -nary Q -generated weight function w_Q using (5).

Step 3: Determine an appropriate function $\sigma : \{1, \dots, nm - 1, nm\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\} \times \{1, \dots, m\}$ that satisfies for any $1 \leq i < j \leq nm$, $E(\sigma(i)) \geq E(\sigma(j))$.

Step 4: Carry out OWA operator with Q to obtain a final evaluation as

$$\text{OWA}_Q(E) = \sum_{i=1}^{nm} w(i) E(\sigma(i)). \quad (14)$$

Example 4.1. For Model 3, we go through the following 4 steps.

Step 1: With the 4×3 evaluation matrix $E = [E(i, j)]$ as in Example 3.1 and RIM quantifier Q such that $Q(t) = t^2$.

Step 2: Create the 12-nary Q -generated weight function w_Q using (5) to obtain

$$w_Q = \left(\frac{1}{144}, \frac{3}{144}, \frac{5}{144}, \frac{7}{144}, \frac{9}{144}, \frac{11}{144}, \frac{13}{144}, \frac{15}{144}, \frac{17}{144}, \frac{19}{144}, \frac{21}{144}, \frac{23}{144} \right).$$

Step 3: Determine an appropriate function $\sigma : \{1, \dots, 11, 12\} \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, 4\} \times \{1, 2, 3\}$ that satisfies for any $1 \leq i < j \leq 12$, $E(\sigma(i)) \geq E(\sigma(j))$. Clearly,

$$\sigma = ((2, 2), (3, 3), (1, 2), (2, 1), (3, 1), (1, 1), (2, 3), (4, 3), (1, 3), (3, 2), (4, 1), (4, 2))$$

is such a function.

Step 4: Carry out OWA operator with Q to obtain a final evaluation as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{OWA}_Q(E) &= \sum_{i=1}^{12} w(i) E(\sigma(i)) \\ &= \frac{1}{144} [(1)(1) + (3)(1) + (5)(0.9) + (7)(0.8) + (9)(0.7) + (11)(0.6) \\ &\quad + (13)(0.5) + (15)(0.5) + (17)(0.4) + (19)(0.4) + (21)(0.3) + (23)(0.2)] \\ &= \frac{1}{144}(66.3) = 0.4604. \end{aligned}$$

4.2. Whole-consideration preference aggregation for evaluation matrix with staggered ordering

In Model 3, one observes that it is possible that the entries in one row, i.e., $E_i(1), \dots, E_i(m)$, are the most m largest entries of all the entries in evaluation matrix E . This phenomenon may be not suitable or comfortable in some decisional situations or for the attitudes and preferences of certain decision makers. Different evaluation methods and preference mod-

els are suitable for different circumstances and decision makers, thus more reasonable methods, especially those mathematically sound and aesthetic ones, are very appealing to the studies and developments of both evaluation methodologies and computational intelligences.

In this part, we introduce another preference evaluation based on a “staggered ordering”. Recall in dictionary definition, “stagger” means “to arrange something so that they do not all begin and end at the same time”. By this figurative motivation, we next define some necessary permutations for given evaluation matrix $E = [E(i, j)]$, followed by the direct proposal of the explicit aggregation formula.

Model 4.2. Whole-consideration preference aggregation for evaluation matrix with staggered ordering.

Step 1: Select a desired RIM quantifier Q representing the optimism/pessimism attitude of decision maker, whose quasi-orness indicates the extent of such attitude.

Step 2: Create the nm -nary Q -generated weight function w_Q using (5).

Step 3: Given evaluation matrix $E = [E(i, j)]$ ($i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$), define $\sigma = (\sigma_i)_{i=1}^n$ to be a vector formed by n permutations on $\{1, \dots, m\}$ such that for any $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ we have $E(i, \sigma_i(s)) \geq E(i, \sigma_i(t))$ whenever $1 \leq s < t \leq m$. Then, define $\eta = (\eta_j)_{j=1}^m$ to be a vector formed by m permutations on $\{1, \dots, n\}$ such that for any $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ we have

$$E(\eta_j(s), \sigma_{\eta_j(s)}(j)) \geq E(\eta_j(t), \sigma_{\eta_j(t)}(j)) \quad \text{whenever } 1 \leq s < t \leq n. \quad (15)$$

Step 4: Carry out preference aggregation with Q to obtain a final evaluation by

$$\sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n w(i + (j - 1)n) \cdot E(\eta_j(i), \sigma_{\eta_j(i)}(j)). \quad (16)$$

Example 4.2. With the same evaluation matrix and RIM quantifier to those in Example 4.1, the first two steps will be omitted. We next carry out Step 3 and Step 4 in detail.

Step 3: With given evaluation matrix $E = [E(i, j)]$ ($i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$), define $\sigma = (\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4)$ such that $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = (2, 1, 3)$, $\sigma_3 = \sigma_4 = (3, 1, 2)$. Then, define $\eta = (\eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3)$ such that $\eta_1 = \eta_2 = (2, 3, 1, 4)$, $\eta_3 = (2, 1, 3, 4)$.

Step 4: Carry out preference aggregation with Q to obtain a final evaluation by

using (16):

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{j=1}^3 \sum_{i=1}^4 w(i + 4(j - 1)) \cdot E(\eta_j(i), \sigma_{\eta_j(i)}(j)) \\
&= w(1)E(2, 2) + w(2)E(3, 3) + w(3)E(1, 2) + w(4)E(4, 3) \\
&\quad + w(5)E(2, 1) + w(6)E(3, 1) + w(7)E(1, 1) + w(8)E(4, 1) \\
&\quad + w(9)E(2, 3) + w(10)E(1, 3) + w(11)E(3, 2) + w(12)E(4, 2) \\
&= \frac{1}{144} [(1)(1) + (3)(1) + (5)(0.9) + (7)(0.5) \\
&\quad + (9)(0.8) + (11)(0.7) + (13)(0.6) + (15)(0.5) \\
&\quad + (17)(0.5) + (19)(0.4) + (21)(0.4) + (23)(0.2)] \\
&= \frac{1}{144}(71.3) = 0.4951.
\end{aligned}$$

Comparing the two above discussed methods in this section, we find that the related ordering or weights arrangement in Model 4 are more “even” for all rows than in Model 3. Nevertheless, as computational intelligence cannot avoid the considerations to and concerns for human mental subjectivity and course of behavior, there is no perfect or the best choice for desired preference models. Instead, the preferences with more reasonability, robust or flexibility, etc., clearly are more interesting to be considered. In addition, it is also important that the choice for preference models should also depend upon detailed situations, such as requirements and restrictions, which will be further studied in later works.

5. Conclusions

In multi-criteria and multi-sources evaluation problem, every entry (or input) in evaluation matrix under aggregation belongs to a certain criterion and as well to a certain sources. With such a two dimensional structure, traditionally used OWA operators need to be further adapted. When a RIM quantifier is given to represent the subjectivity of decision maker, this study discussed four preference aggregation models to be carried out and to obtain some final comprehensive evaluation from given inputs and preference.

The first one model is more similar to commonly used method in multi-criteria group evaluation where two weight functions are often given for criteria and group respectively. However, the weight functions obtained in this model are generated from two different RIM quantifiers, embodying corresponding optimism/pessimism attitude of decision makers.

The second model still considers the two dimensions, but it regards each row of evaluation matrix as a vector and hence the matrix also forms a vector lattice. Then, we apply some recently published results about OWA aggregation on lattice to MCMSE problem.

Note that the first two models can be also dually devised.

The next model slightly swerves attention to another view on the evaluation matrix, viewing all the entries as elements in a bigger vector and ignoring the presences of criteria and sources. Thus, directly employing an nm -nary OWA operator, we propose a broad and whole perspective to consider MCMSE problem.

The last model revolves around the repetitive definitions of two collections of permutations which successfully rearrange the entries in evaluation matrix, providing more choice to decision makers and add some new formulations to the theory of aggregation functions.

When the decision making and evaluation problems will be with more restrictive conditions or given information, the evaluation models proposed in this study can be also used in, adapted to or combined with those additional decisional contexts, which will be studied in later works.

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